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This month has been extremely active for BIOSYSMO including two large conferences that boosted our project's dissemination in numerous peers in the field of bioremediation and environmental science.

CLOSE COLLABORATION WITH OUR EU BIOREMEDIATION CLUSTER AT BIOBIO CONFERENCE 2024!

Our EU Bioremediation Cluster, which includes six EU-funded projects (**NYPHE**, **SYMBIOREM**, **MIBIREM**, **EDAPHOS**, **ISLANDR**, and **BIOSYSMO**), had the opportunity to participate as a united cluster group in the 7th International Symposium on Biosorption and Biodegradation/Bioremediation, BioBio2024. This conference served as a platform to showcase our cluster's research, introducing our projects and our dedicated efforts towards a cleaner environment. Soil pollution remains a critical issue, gaining attention as more people become environmentally conscious and eager to support and participate in initiatives like ours.

BioBio2024, held from June 16-20, 2024, in Prague, brought together numerous researchers focused on biosorption, biodegradation, and biodeterioration, who presented their work and the latest scientific advancements in the field. CIIMAR, UPM, LEITAT, UBFC, UBU and IDENER represented BIOSYSMO with engaging presentations and posters.

This event marked a significant milestone for our EU Bioremediation Cluster as all projects shared their advancements and insights so far in an one-day workshop in plenary session. This workshop was an excellent opportunity

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to showcase our various approaches to the bioremediation of soil, water, and sediments, and, most importantly, the practical application to polluted sites needing our intervention.

We extend our heartfelt gratitude to Dr. Akanksha Mishra and Dr. Rocio Barros representing BIOSYSMO, and for effectively highlighting our project's capabilities.

The peak moments from our workshop include our cluster success stories, which has highly helped in building public trust in research & biotechnology and our comprehensive approaches:

- Extending beyond bioremediation and addressing the overall soil health
- Emphasising on the implications of soil health and groundwater contamination in our daily lives

Finally, a crucial dialogue revealed the gap between biotechnological innovations and their practical application, calling for greater involvement from the industry and intermediary producers.

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BIOSYSMO shines at CONDEGRES 2024

Our BIOSYSMO partner University of Burgos was the organiser of the 10th National Symposium on Control of Soil Degradation and Recovery (CONDEGRES 2024), taking place in Burgos, Spain, 24-27 of June 2024. This symposium served as a prominent forum for cutting-edge advancements in soil degradation control and recovery techniques.

Dr. Marta Franco from IDENER presented BIOSYSMO's progress with her talk titled "Bioremediation systems exploiting synergies for enhanced removal of mixed pollutants," and her poster titled "Unificando información para avanzar en el estudio de la biorremediación del suelo" contributing significantly to the discourse on soil recovery techniques.

Special thanks to Dr. Rocio Barros, from ICCRAM-UBU, for organising this fundamental event that led to insightful conversations and collaborations with other projects.

A key feature of the symposium was the dissemination corner of the conference, where among diverse projects, BIOSYSMO and our cluster project SYMBIOREM were there! This dedicated area offered attendees a comprehensive view of the collective efforts towards a healthier environment and also promoted our cluster's activities. Additionally, all attendees were provided with USB sticks engraved with the BIOSYSMO and the conference logo. This initiative further extended the outreach of our project to a broader audience interested in the fields of bioremediation.

It was a great opportunity for networking as CONDEGRES 2024 offered a platform for researchers and stakeholders to discuss and exchange ideas on the latest developments in soil degradation control and recovery.